

TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF BASALT FIBRES AFTER THERMAL TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article is an experimental investigation of the effects of temperature and atmosphere on the tensile behaviour of basalt fibres. The heating conditions were chosen in order to replicate those typically used in thermal recycling of polymer matrix composites. The change of properties is assessed at room temperature on fibres heat-treated for 1 h up to 600 °C in air and in argon. The loss in fibre strength was found to be affected by both temperature and atmosphere while the modulus of thermally-treated basalt fibres increased with conditioning temperature and these effects have been discussed in terms of decomposition of the organic sizing and structural relaxation during thermal treatment. X-ray diffraction excluded the effect of crystallization on the mechanical behaviour of the fibres after thermal exposure. Scanning electron microscopy showed that failure for all heat treatments was caused by surface flaws.

1 INTRODUCTION

Europe's production volume in glass fibre reinforced plastics (GRPs) reached 1.069 megatonnes in 2015, representing the highest level in eight years [1]. Considering the world market, glass fibre reinforced thermoset composites account for about 90 % of all the composites currently produced and these are traditionally directed to landfill at their end of life, mainly because recycling operations are often difficult and expensive [2]. Despite such technical and economic issues, there is a growing environmental pressure to ban or at least limit the disposal of waste composites via land fill. It is therefore not surprising the growth of a number of methods to recycle composites over the last years [3–7]. Among these methods, pyrolysis is likely the most preferred technique to recycle composites with the objective to reclaim fibres that represent the most valuable part of the waste. This process allows the recovery of carbon fibres largely maintaining their reinforcement capability, whilst glass fibres are usually quite damaged. In particular, the tensile strength is reduced to a great extent (~ 50–80%) [2,8–13] and this aspect seriously affects their potential reuse as fibrous reinforcement in new structural composite materials. Pyrolysis basically involves the matrix degradation at high temperature (typically 400–550 °C) in the absence of air to produce oil, gases and solid products (fibres, fillers and char). The fibres are usually contaminated by this char and require a post-treatment in air in a furnace at least at 450 °C to oxidize the residual char and remove surface contamination. The mechanisms responsible for the loss in fibre strength represent a much debated issue in literature and two main mechanisms have been proposed: (i) thermally-activated changes to the anisotropic silica network structure initially created by the high drawing stress during fibre manufacture [12–15] and (ii) thermally-induced diffusion of water into the fibre surface leading to increased surface area and larger micropores [11,16,17]. In an attempt to shed light on this important issue, recently Feih et al. [2] compared the tensile strength of heat-treated glass fibres with that of fibres containing a single nano-sized surface flaw of controlled size artificially created by focussed ion beam (FIB) milling. The authors concluded that bulk changes (such as a change in fracture toughness or fibre modulus) influencing the stress–flaw relationship for E-glass fibres do not occur during thermal recycling and therefore the reduction in fibre tensile strength during thermal conditioning can be attributed solely to thermally-activated growth of surface flaws. This growth, according to the authors, is ascribed to the

diffusion of water molecules in the glass fibre structure and their subsequent reaction with stressed siloxane bonds at the crack tip.

In an attempt to reduce the environmental impact of synthetic polymers and reinforcements, there has been a resurgent interest in the use of natural fibres in polymer matrices [18]. Many types of natural fibres like sisal, kenaf, hemp, flax, jute have been studied and applied but lignocellulosic fibres are very sensitive to thermal and hygroscopic loads and show limited and variable mechanical properties due to the plant growing and harvesting conditions, the fibre extraction process, the variable fibre shape and geometry. Another drawback is the chemical incompatibility with many hydrophobic polymer matrices which results in a low fibre/matrix interface strength and limited stress transfer efficiency. A possible solution that takes into account the environmental issues is represented by the use of natural fibres but of mineral origin, like basalt. The basalt fibre is an environmentally friendly material characterized by excellent sound insulation properties, resistance to heat greater than that offered by glass fibres and a good chemical inertia [19]. As regards the mechanical properties, basalt fibres compare quite favourable with traditional E-glass fibres, at the expense of a slightly higher density [19,20]. Basalt fibre is superior to E-glass for high operating temperature limit (~650 °C for basalt compared to ~460 °C for E-glass), and higher softening temperature (1050 °C for basalt and 600 °C for E-glass). This often claimed higher thermal stability and resistance of basalt fibres compared to glass ones could provide in principle basalt fibres with better prospects to survive a pyrolysis treatment, thus having the chance to be re-used in valuable products. Despite the potential high temperature applications of basalt fibres, their mechanical properties retention after a thermal exposure is not known in detail. In particular, it is not completely understood whether the higher operating and softening temperatures of basalt fibres result into superior tensile strength retention properties after a thermal treatment.

While the strength loss of E-glass fibres due to exposure to high temperature has been well documented in literature, less information are available for basalt fibres. Most of these papers addressed the thermal response of basalt tows (bundles) [21–24]. Bhat et al. [24] tested at room temperature basalt tows previously heated to temperatures ranging from 150 to 650 °C for times up to two hours and compared the results with those obtained for glass tows in the same experimental conditions. The authors found that the failure load of both tows began to decrease after exposure to 250 °C and the reduction was much more severe with increasing temperature up to 650 °C. They concluded that there were no significant differences in strength loss between basalt and glass tows. Kessler et al. [25] performed tensile tests with impregnated rovings. Before being impregnated, basalt rovings were maintained for two hours at temperatures between 100 °C and 600 °C in air. Up to 300 °C the decrease in tensile strength was limited but between 300 °C and 400 °C the tensile strength of impregnated basalt rovings was found to decrease significantly, exhibiting at 600 °C a lower absolute tensile strength compared to E-glass rovings. Usually the onset of crystallization phenomena is reported to be the cause of such behaviour of basalt fibres after thermal exposure [22,23,25]. Recently Jenkins et al. [26] performed a detailed experimental campaign aimed at comparing the tensile strength retention of single basalt and E-glass fibres after high temperature exposure. They found a good strength retention after a heat treatment at 300 °C (for 20 min) but a sharp decrease at higher temperatures for both fibres (600 °C), with strength losses of 65 % and 80 % for glass and basalt fibres, respectively. Differences in tow strength could be likely due to the sizing and related friction effects between fibres during testing rather than to the single fibre strength. In addition, differences in sizing between different fibres can definitely play a role in determining the final mechanical properties of single fibres. In view of all these issues, the aim of the present work is to study the effect of thermal recycling processing conditions on the properties of single basalt fibres. The variation of the mechanical behaviour was determined following treatments at different temperatures (200 - 600 °C) for a total heating time of 1 h and different furnace atmospheres (air and argon). These conditions were chosen in order to simulate those used in industrial thermal recycling processes.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Raw materials

The effects of temperature and atmosphere on fibre properties were investigated using basalt fibres of commercial grade supplied by Kamenny Vek as a continuous roving with a nominal fibre diameter of 13 μm , linear density of 1200 tex and sized with a commercial epoxy resin compatible sizing (BCF13).

2.2 Fibre heat treatment

Fibre bundles were heat treated as-received in a tube furnace (Lenton Thermal Designs Ltd) with controllable temperature and atmosphere. The effect of the furnace atmosphere was assessed by heating the fibres in high purity argon and ambient air. All fibres were thermally treated at a temperature of 200, 300, 400, 500 and 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in air for 1h, and then removed from the furnace and allowed to cool in room temperature air. The treatment in argon was performed at temperatures of 400, 500 and 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a duration of one hour. The argon atmosphere was chosen to replicate the initial stage of the thermal recycling process of composites when heating is performed under inert conditions in order to decompose the matrix. The ambient air reproduces the second stage when the fibres are heat-treated in air to remove residual char and contamination from the surface.

2.3 Single fibre tensile testing

Tensile properties of virgin and thermally treated fibres were determined in accordance with ASTM C1557. Single fibres were carefully separated by hand from the fibre bundles. Tensile tests were carried out at room temperature by means of a Zwick/Roell Z010 equipped with a 200 N load cell. Tests were performed in displacement control at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min. Individual fibres were glued onto a card tab with a central window cut out to match the gauge length of 20, 30 and 40 mm. At least 20 fibres were tested for each kind of basalt fibre and heating condition. Single fibres were fixed to the card at both sides of the window using LoctiteTM Gel Superglue. Fibre diameter was evaluated through an optical microscope Nikon Eclipse 150L equipped with the image analysis software Lucia Measurement. The cross-sectional area of each fibre was calculated from individual average fibre diameters measured at five points along the gauge length. The actual specimen elongation in the gauge length was determined by subtracting the displacement associated with the system compliance from the total cross-head displacement. The system compliance was measured according to ASTM C1557 by obtaining the force versus displacement behaviour of the fibres at three gauge lengths, namely 20 mm, 30 mm and 40 mm. For each gauge length 30 fibres were tested. The evaluated testing device compliance was 0.0149 mmN⁻¹.

The scatter of the Young's modulus and tensile strength was statistically analysed using a two-parameter Weibull distribution, according to the equation (1):

$$F(\chi) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\chi}{\chi_0}\right)^\alpha\right] \quad (1)$$

where $F(\chi)$ is the probability of failure of the parameter χ , α is the Weibull modulus and χ_0 represents a scale parameter. The probability of failure was estimated using the following estimator (equation (2))

$$F_j = \frac{j - 0.5}{N} \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of tested fibres and j is the rank of the j th data point. This is generally recommended because it is essentially independent of sample size for sample sizes greater than 20 [27].

A single set of parameters for each property (tensile strength or Young's modulus), χ_0 and α , was obtained from the intercept and slope, respectively, of the plot $\ln\{\ln[1/(1-F)]\}$ against $\ln(\chi)$.

2.4 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Analysis of the mass loss of fibres with temperature was carried out using a SetSys Evolution (Setaram Instrumentation) thermogravimetric analyser. The fibres were placed in a platinum pan and heated at a rate of 10 °C/min to a maximum temperature of 600 °C in air and in argon atmosphere.

2.5 X-ray diffraction (XRD)

To identify the crystalline phases and their formation sequence, basalt fibres were heat treated at 500, 600, 700, 800, 900 and 1000 °C for 1 h in air. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of thermally treated fibres was performed at room temperature on a Philips X'Pert PRO powder diffractometer with a X'Celerator PW 3015 detector (Cu_{K1} α radiation = 1.54060 Å, Cu_{K2} α radiation = 1.54443 Å). XRD patterns were collected in the range of $2\theta = 10^\circ\text{--}70^\circ$ with a scan step $2\theta = 0.02^\circ$ and scan rate of 1°/min.

2.6 Density measurement

In order to evaluate possible variations of density of basalt fibres subjected to thermal treatment, the density was measured by helium pycnometry (AccuPyc 1330). The density measurements involved both the non-heat-treated fibres and those treated at 200, 300, 400, 500 and 600 °C.

2.7 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

After tensile testing, the fracture surfaces of the fibres were examined using a scanning electron microscope Philips XL40. All specimens were sputter coated with gold prior to examination.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical properties of untreated basalt fibres

In order to evaluate the effects of different heat treatments on the mechanical properties of basalt fibres, initially tensile tests were carried out on untreated fibres at three different gauge lengths. In tables 1 and 2 are reported the results from the tensile tests as well as the values of the characteristic parameters of the Weibull distribution. Optical microscopy measurements pointed out the existence of a significant scatter in fibre diameter, with actual values different from the nominal ones. Diameter of fibres is a very important parameter for the correct evaluation of the mechanical properties and this value is influenced by different production process parameters, such as the speed of molten basalt flow and the uneven distribution of the sizing on fibre surface.

Gauge length (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Strain at failure (%)
20	13.33 (1.21)	2307.76 (351.51)	72.20 (4.59)	3.01 (0.60)
30	13.94 (1.45)	2097.22 (294.23)	70.15 (5.72)	2.85 (0.36)
40	13.44 (1.36)	1804.82 (264.77)	69.57 (6.00)	2.49 (0.35)

Table 1: Summary of tensile properties of untreated basalt fibres (figures in parenthesis represent standard deviation).

Gauge length (mm)	Tensile strength – α_σ	Tensile strength – σ_0	Young's modulus – α_E	Young's modulus – E_0
20	7.90	2451.67	19.27	74.23
30	8.54	2220.18	14.84	72.66
40	8.18	1914.03	13.78	72.28

Table 2: Weibull distribution parameters for untreated basalt fibres.

The measured strengths of basalt fibres are typical of fibres currently being produced, with values exceeding 2 GPa at room temperature [26]. It is worth noting the dependence of tensile strength on gauge length. At short gauge lengths the strength values are higher and decrease with an increase of the fibre length, while no significant dependence was detected for the Young's modulus. This is the demonstration of the dimension effect on the strength of brittle basalt fibres, as observed for other ceramic fibres, including glass fibres [28, 29]. Weibull modulus for tensile strength was found to range from 7 to 8, higher compared to what usually reported for glass fibres (3-5) [28, 30] and carbon fibres (3-6) [31] but lower compared to the values of other high performance ceramic fibres, such as Nextel™ (8-12) [32]. Weibull theory predicts that fibres with greater diameter should, on average, have a greater chance to have a large flaw, and will therefore be weaker than smaller fibres. In addition, because diameter was experimentally found to vary from fibre to fibre even within a tow, testing fibres at constant gauge length does not assure a constant tested volume. Thus, the measured strength distribution is to be considered as the overlap of the dispersion of strength due to the volumetric distribution of flaws and due to the variable fibre volume. Because of this effect, the actual distribution of fibre strength is artificially broadened, lowering the measured Weibull modulus. No clear dependence of Weibull modulus on gauge length was found for basalt fibres, as supported by other researches on different ceramic fibres [28, 29].

Weibull distribution plots of strength and Young's modulus for untreated single basalt fibres as a function of gauge length are reported in figure 1.

Figure 1: Weibull plots of single fibre strength and Young's modulus for BCF13 fibres.

A linear trend was detected thus suggesting the validity of a unimodal Weibull function with few exceptions for very low strength values. Such deviations have been the subject of numerous discussions over the years [33, 34], and generally they have been ascribed to two main causes, namely the presence of more than one failure mode in the material or that the threshold stress, which is usually set to zero for brittle materials, is not zero and therefore a three parameter Weibull distribution should be used. As recently discussed by Thomason [33], it is not entirely correct to infer sound conclusions on the fracture process of the fibres from Weibull graphs because the Weibull theory is a statistical one without being based on the physics of the fracture process [35]. This means that Weibull plots are useful to support the existence of several fracture modes only if additional information are available. To this purpose, the lateral surface of virgin fibres and cross-section of the fracture surface after single fibre tensile tests were investigated by scanning electron microscopy. Most fibres, both low strength and high strength fibres, showed a typical and common fracture pattern (figure 2a). Distinctive markings were found, which are all compatible with a failure caused by surface flaws. The crack front propagated through the material, originating three different regions, namely mirror, mist and hackle as commonly reported for brittle materials, in particular for glass fibres [30,36]. For most fracture surfaces investigated, the location of the fracture mirror suggests that fracture originated from the surface of the basalt fibres, thus confirming the existence of a single common failure source.

For glass fibres [12, 30, 34] it has been shown that different film formers and coupling agent/film

former combinations on the surface of fibres can significantly affect the mechanical properties of the resulting fibres themselves due to a different healing effect for surface flaws. The crucial role played by the silane based sizing layer has been previously studied by Wang and Jones [37]. They showed that such sizing is made up of three different layers: a physisorbed layer, a cross-linked and an interfacial layer. According to Zinc et al. [38] these three layers can influence the effect of surface defects on the mechanical properties of the fibres because they can fully or partially fill the surface cavities. It is clear that sizings characterized by different chemical compositions may have a different filling capacity of the surface defects of the fibres. A morphological analysis carried out by SEM showed that the fibres have a very regular and even surface finish, figure 2b.

Figure 2: Scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surface and of the lateral surface of BCF13 fibres without heat treatment.

3.3 Mechanical properties of heat treated basalt fibres

After thermal exposure in air, single basalt fibres were meticulously separated from the fibre bundles and glued onto a card tab with a central window cut out of 20 mm. As found for glass fibres by Jenkins et al. [9], a significant drop of the tensile strength of the different basalt fibres with increasing temperature has been recorded. From figure 3 it can be inferred that passing from room temperature up to 200 °C, BCF13 fibres exhibited a reduction in tensile strength around 26 %. The tensile strength continued monotonically to decrease with increasing temperature up to the maximum temperature of 600°C where a strength loss of about 75 % was measured.

Figure 3: Tensile strength as a function of heating temperature in air for single basalt fibres.

These values compare quite favourably with those reported for glass fibres [2,9,11,12,26] and the one reported for basalt fibres [26]. The strength of basalt fibres tended to converge as the thermal

conditioning temperature increased and this can support the role played by the deterioration of the surface coating due to the thermal exposure. The fibres experienced a significant and rapid strength loss after heat treatments performed up to 400°C. Further increase in temperature up to 500°C did not caused a marked strength loss which instead was found to increase again in the temperature range 500°C-600°C. The Weibull analysis was performed also for thermally treated fibres (table 3, 4) and again a linear trend was observed which indicates that the mechanical behaviour of the fibres is still influenced by the presence of a single population of defects and that the temperature increase does not involve a change in the nature of defects, but rather it can affect their concentration and severity (figure 4).

Temperature (°C)	Tensile strength $-\alpha_\sigma$	Tensile strength $-\sigma_0$	Young's modulus $-\alpha_E$	Young's modulus $-E_0$
400	3.90	1032.62	24.91	83.39
500	10.10	1042.49	16.33	89.47
600	3.03	639.92	18.28	88.52

Table 3: Weibull distribution parameters for treated basalt fibres (air).

Temperature (°C)	Tensile strength $-\alpha_\sigma$	Tensile strength $-\sigma_0$	Young's modulus $-\alpha_E$	Young's modulus $-E_0$
400	5.82	1539.13	27.04	77.65
500	4.49	1317.56	36.53	78.22
600	3.62	719.41	26.62	83.42

Table 4: Weibull distribution parameters for treated basalt fibres (argon).

Figure 4: Weibull plots of single fibre strength and Young's modulus for treated basalt fibres.

As a confirmation, figure 5 reports representative fracture surfaces of basalt fibres after heat treatment at 300°C and 600°C. The mirror, mist and hackle regions were present in every investigated fibre fracture regardless of heat-treatment condition, thus suggesting a failure process not affected by temperature. The only significant difference caused by the different treatment conditions was the size of the mirror zone. It was observed that the size of the mirror zone increased with the increasing of temperature and decreasing of the fibre strength. This increase can be ascribed to an increase in the size of surface defects during heat treatment [11].

Figure 5: Scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surfaces of BCF13 basalt fibres after treatment at different temperatures.

When dealing with glass fibres, the loss of protective sizing during high temperature exposure is usually reported as one of the factors contributing to the strength loss observed [9,12]. This appears to hold also for basalt fibres, as confirmed by the thermogravimetric results shown in figure 6. The basalt fibres exhibited a two-stage sizing degradation: an initial rapid mass loss between approximately 160°C–400°C followed by a second, with markedly slower rate, between 400°C–500°C. It is clear that the removal of organic coating is only one of the mechanisms that are responsible for the strength loss, which can be active in the lower temperature range but not at higher temperatures (>450°C), where the volatilization is already almost complete. The strength reduction occurring at higher temperatures is to be ascribed to some additional fundamental mechanisms. Other works on stone wool fibres with a basalt-like composition [39,40] showed that oxidation can take place at temperatures higher than 500°C. This phenomenon is related to the oxidation of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺. Indeed, the presence of iron oxides represents one of the main differences in chemical composition between glass and basalt fibres. This oxidation process was confirmed also in the present study, as from the TGA (figure 5) it is evident an increase in mass at temperatures higher than 500°C, which is due to the incorporation of oxygen in the fibres. In stone wool fibres this oxidation was reported to lead to the formation of a nanocrystalline surface layer able to lower the activation energy for crystallisation, thus dominating the crystallization behaviour of the fibres.

Figure 6: Mass loss for BCF13 fibres measured by TGA in air and in argon.

In the present work, in order to assess the possible development of crystalline phases in heat-treated basalt fibres and to establish a potential relationship between crystalline phases and tensile strength loss, diffraction analysis (XRD) was conducted on basalt fibres, whose results are summarized in figure 7. Basalt fibres exhibited a fully amorphous structure up to 700°C and crystallization started

beyond 800°C, in accordance with what reported by Manylov et al. [41]. Based on these findings, it is unlikely that crystallization can be used to explain the measured strength loss behaviour, as temperatures in excess of 800 °C are needed. In addition, a similar trend in strength loss was also observed for basalt fibres heat treated in inert (argon) atmosphere, where no oxidation is expected to occur, as supported by the TGA curve shown in figures 5. The data reveal no increase in mass and a less mass loss rate for fibres heated in argon, thus suggesting a slower decomposition rate for the sizing in the absence of oxygen.

Figure 7: X-ray diffraction patterns for basalt fibres heat treated in the temperature range 500-1000°C for 1 h in air.

This behaviour is reflected in the lower strength loss in argon compared to air (figure 8), even if fibre strength was reduced by the heat-treatment regardless of the atmosphere.

If oxidation and crystallization cannot be appealed for explaining the observed strength loss occurring at the highest temperatures, it is reasonable to suppose the existence of some form of structural rearrangement [14]. In this regard, relaxation of structural anisotropy and enthalpy relaxation due to high temperature exposure can be both possible at different extents and rates [15], with structural relaxation occurring at faster rates and at lower temperatures. These two phenomena originate from the high cooling rate during fibre drawing which can induce a certain degree of preferred structural and defect orientation along the fibre axis. Structural relaxation involves both local structural rearrangements and change in defect orientation towards a random state with much more probability of leading to a catastrophic failure. Enthalpy relaxation is instead due to relaxation of the silicate network. The higher the starting anisotropy of the fibre (increase in fibre drawing speed), the easier the relaxation, which in case of structural relaxation can take place already at temperatures equal to $0.5 T_g$ [42]. These phenomena could explain the observed strength loss in basalt fibres which are characterized by T_g around 900-980 K [14,41]. The exact nature of these mechanisms needs a further and deeper investigation as well as their relationship with strength loss.

Figure 8: Tensile strength of basalt fibres as a function of temperature and furnace atmosphere.

An indirect evidence of the existence of structural arrangements caused by thermal exposure can be obtained by considering the variation of Young's modulus with increasing temperature (figure 9a). It was found an increasing trend with increasing temperature that suggests a thermal compaction phenomenon, already reported in glass fibres [12,43,44] and therefore likely active also in basalt fibres as confirmed in the present study by the systematic increase in basalt fibre density (figure 9b) measured by helium pycnometry [45].

Figure 9: Young's modulus (a) and density (b) as a function of temperature for basalt fibres treated in air.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The strength loss of continuous basalt fibres with commercial sizing optimized for epoxy matrices was assessed following a 1 hour heat treatment in the temperature range 200-600°C in two different furnace atmospheres, namely air and argon. These operating conditions were selected in order to mimic those potentially experienced by fibres during a recycling process by pyrolysis. The basalt fibres showed a failure process dominated by a single population of defects mostly originating on the fibre surface as supported by the SEM analysis of the fracture surfaces, even after exposure to high temperatures. The final values of strength retention of tensile strength were comparable with those reported for glass fibres, even if in most studies on glass fibres the duration of exposure to high temperature was much lower compared to the present study. The effect of time has been proved to influence markedly the strength retention at each temperature level [11], therefore basalt fibres can show better chances to survive a recycling step by pyrolysis.

Heat treatment of basalt fibres revealed a rapid reduction in the fracture stress with increasing temperature up to 400°C, which was found to depend on both temperature and heating atmosphere. The progressive loss of the strength of heat treated basalt fibres has been interpreted as a combination of surface damage caused by manual handling following sizing degradation and structural rearrangement. As regards the second mechanism, the onset of significant oxidation triggering early crystallization of basal fibres was excluded by XRD analysis. The heat treatment-induced decay of tensile strength was proposed to be ascribed to structural anisotropy relaxation (local structural arrangement and defect reorientation), even if this potential strength controlling mechanism requires specific and further investigation.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Witten, *Composites Market Report 2015*, 2015.
- [2] S. Feih, A. P. Mouritz, and S. W. Case, Determining the mechanism controlling glass fibre strength loss during thermal recycling of waste composites, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 76, pp. 255–261, Sep. 2015.
- [3] J. M. Henshaw, W. Han, and A. D. Owens, An Overview of Recycling Issues for Composite Materials, *J. Thermoplast. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 4–20, Jan. 1996.
- [4] Y. Yang, R. Boom, B. Irion, D.-J. van Heerden, P. Kuiper, and H. de Wit, Recycling of composite materials, *Chem. Eng. Process. Process Intensif.*, vol. 51, pp. 53–68, Jan. 2012.
- [5] S. J. Pickering, Recycling technologies for thermoset composite materials—current status, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 37, no. 8, pp. 1206–1215, Aug. 2006.
- [6] E. Asmatulu, J. Twomey, and M. Overcash, Recycling of fiber-reinforced composites and direct structural composite recycling concept, *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 593–608, Feb. 2013.
- [7] G. Oliveux, L. O. Dandy, and G. A. Leeke, Current Status of Recycling of Fibre Reinforced Polymers: review of technologies, reuse and resulting properties, *Prog. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 72, pp. 61–99, Mar. 2015.
- [8] W. Thomas, An investigation of the factors affecting the strength of glass fiber, *Glas. Ceram.*, vol. 1, pp. 4–18, 1960.
- [9] P. G. Jenkins, L. Yang, J. J. Liggat, and J. L. Thomason, Investigation of the strength loss of glass fibre after thermal conditioning, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 1050–1057, Oct. 2015.
- [10] S. Feih, A. P. Mouritz, Z. Mathys, and A. G. Gibson, Tensile Strength Modeling of Glass Fiber Polymer Composites in Fire, *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 41, no. 19, pp. 2387–2410, Jul. 2007.
- [11] S. Feih, E. Boiocchi, G. Mathys, Z. Mathys, A. G. Gibson, and A. P. Mouritz, Mechanical properties of thermally-treated and recycled glass fibres, *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 350–358, Apr. 2011.
- [12] J. L. Thomason, L. Yang, and R. Meier, The properties of glass fibres after conditioning at composite recycling temperatures, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 61, pp. 201–208, Jun. 2014.
- [13] J. L. Thomason, C. C. Kao, J. Ure, and L. Yang, The strength of glass fibre reinforcement after exposure to elevated composite processing temperatures, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 153–162, Sep. 2013.
- [14] M. D. Lund and Y. Yue, Impact of Drawing Stress on the Tensile Strength of Oxide Glass Fibers, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, vol. 93, no. 10, pp. 3236–3243, Oct. 2010.
- [15] M. Ya, J. Deubener, and Y. Yue, Enthalpy and Anisotropy Relaxation of Glass Fibers, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, vol. 91, no. 3, pp. 745–752, Mar. 2008.
- [16] M. Tomozawa and R. W. Hepburn, Surface structural relaxation of silica glass: a possible mechanism of mechanical fatigue, *J. Non. Cryst. Solids*, vol. 345–346, pp. 449–460, Oct. 2004.
- [17] R. Gy, Stress corrosion of silicate glass: a review, *J. Non. Cryst. Solids*, vol. 316, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Feb. 2003.
- [18] K. L. Pickering, M. G. Aruan Efendy, and T. M. Le, A review of recent developments in natural fibre composites and their mechanical performance, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, Sep. 2015.
- [19] V. Fiore, T. Scalici, G. Di Bella, and A. Valenza, A review on basalt fibre and its composites, *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 74, pp. 74–94, Jan. 2015.
- [20] V. Dhand, G. Mittal, K. Y. Rhee, and D. Hui, A short review on basalt fiber reinforced polymer composites, *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 73, pp. 166–180, Dec. 2014.
- [21] J. Militký, V. Kovačič, and J. Rubnerová, Influence of thermal treatment on tensile failure of basalt fibers, *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, vol. 69, no. 9, pp. 1025–1033, Jun. 2002.
- [22] M. Cerny, P. Glogar, V. Golias, J. Hruska, P. Jakes, Z. Sucharda, and I. Vavrova, Comparison of mechanical properties and structural changes of continuous basalt and glass fibres at elevated temperatures, *Ceramics*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 82–88, 2007.

- [23] S. Sabet, F. Akhlaghi, and R. Eslami-Farsani, The Effect of Thermal Treatment on Tensile Properties of Basalt Fibers, *J. Ceram. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 245–248, 2015.
- [24] T. Bhat, V. Chevali, X. Liu, S. Feih, and A. P. Mouritz, Fire structural resistance of basalt fibre composite, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 71, pp. 107–115, 2015.
- [25] E. Kessler, R. Gadow, and J. Straub, Basalt, glass and carbon fibers and their fiber reinforced polymer composites under thermal and mechanical load, *AIMS Mater. Sci.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 1561–1576, 2016.
- [26] P. G. Jenkins, S. Riopedre-Méndez, S. Sáez-Rodríguez, L. Yang, and J. L. Thomason, Investigation of the strength of thermally conditioned basalt and e-glass fibres, in *20th International Conference on Composite Materials*, 2015, pp. 1–9.
- [27] J. D. Sullivan and P. H. Lauzon, Experimental probability estimators for Weibull plots, *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, vol. 5, no. 12, pp. 1245–1247, Dec. 1986.
- [28] L. Yang and J. L. Thomason, Effect of silane coupling agent on mechanical performance of glass fibre, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 1947–1954, Mar. 2013.
- [29] M.-H. Berger and D. Jeulin, Statistical analysis of the failure stresses of ceramic fibres: Dependence of the Weibull parameters on the gauge length, diameter variation and fluctuation of defect density, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 38, no. 13, pp. 2913–2923, 2003.
- [30] S. Feih, A. Thrane, and H. Lilholt, Tensile strength and fracture surface characterisation of sized and unsized glass fibers, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 40, no. 7, pp. 1615–1623, Apr. 2005.
- [31] T. Tagawa and T. Miyata, Size effect on tensile strength of carbon fibers, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 238, no. 2, pp. 336–342, 1997.
- [32] D. M. Wilson, Statistical tensile strength of Nextel™ 610 and Nextel™ 720 fibres, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 32, no. 10, pp. 2535–2542, 1997.
- [33] J. L. Thomason, On the application of Weibull analysis to experimentally determined single fibre strength distributions, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 77, pp. 74–80, 2013.
- [34] P. Zinck, E. Mäder, and J. F. Gerard, Role of silane coupling agent and polymeric film former for tailoring glass fiber sizings from tensile strength measurements, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 36, no. 21, pp. 5245–5252, 2001.
- [35] A. Wolfenden and S. van der Zwaag, The Concept of Filament Strength and the Weibull Modulus, *J. Test. Eval.*, vol. 17, no. 5, p. 292, 1989.
- [36] S. Feih, K. Manatpon, Z. Mathys, A. G. Gibson, and A. P. Mouritz, Strength degradation of glass fibers at high temperatures, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 392–400, Jan. 2009.
- [37] D. Wang and F. R. Jones, Surface analytical study of the interaction between γ -amino propyl triethoxysilane and E-glass surface, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 28, no. 9, pp. 2481–2488, 1993.
- [38] P. Zinck, M. F. Pay, R. Rezakhanlou, and J. F. Gerard, Mechanical characterisation of glass fibres as an indirect analysis of the effect of surface treatment, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 34, no. 9, pp. 2121–2133, 1999.
- [39] Y. Yue, M. Korsgaard, L. F. Kirkegaard, and G. Heide, Formation of a Nanocrystalline Layer on the Surface of Stone Wool Fibers, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, vol. 92, no. 1, pp. 62–67, Jan. 2009.
- [40] M. M. Smedskjaer, M. Solvang, and Y. Yue, Crystallisation behaviour and high-temperature stability of stone wool fibres, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 1287–1295, 2010.
- [41] M. S. Manylov, S. I. Gutnikov, K. V. Pokholok, B. I. Lazoryak, and Y. V. Lipatov, Crystallization mechanism of basalt glass fibers in air, *Mendeleev Commun.*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 361–363, Nov. 2013.
- [42] J. Deubener, Y. Yue, H. Bornhöft, and M. Ya, Decoupling between birefringence decay, enthalpy relaxation and viscous flow in calcium boroalumosilicate glasses, *Chem. Geol.*, vol. 256, no. 3, pp. 299–305, 2008.
- [43] L. Yang and J. L. Thomason, The thermal behaviour of glass fibre investigated by thermomechanical analysis, *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 48, no. 17, pp. 5768–5775, Sep. 2013.
- [44] M. L. KorwinEdson, D. A. Hofmann, and P. B. McGinnis, Strength of High Performance Glass Reinforcement Fiber, *Int. J. Appl. Glas. Sci.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 107–121, Jun. 2012.
- [45] T. J. Rude, L. H. Strait, and L. A. Ruhala, Measurement of Fiber Density by Helium Pycnometry, *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 34, no. 22, pp. 1948–1958, Jan. 2000.